

Influence of Steel Recycling on Phase Transformation in Medium-Manganese Third-Generation Advanced High-Strength Steels

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Due to the ensuing shift toward adoption of increased levels of scrap during steel production to reduce the carbon footprint, it is essential that the effects of tramp elements entering the produced steel from the scrap are understood. In this context, effects of four major tramp elements (Ni, Cu, Cr, and Mo) on the phase transformation and the microstructure evolution of medium-manganese steels are studied by theoretical predictions. The results indicate that Cu and Ni are beneficial, whereas Cr and Mo have mixed effects due to the formation of different equilibrium metal carbides. The Cu and Ni concentrations of 0.1–0.5 wt% marginally increase the maximum retained austenite content by 2 vol%. Cr reduces the achievable maximum amount of retained austenite more strongly (decrease by 8 vol% for 0.5 wt% Cr) than Mo (decrease by 4 vol% with 0.5 wt% Mo), and Cr gives a wider processing window for achieving a microstructure with a lower variation than Mo. Combined effects of the elements are to decrease the maximum retained austenite by 8 vol% with lowering of processing temperature by 20 °C. This work provides a guideline for the selection of the optimum processing window of medium-manganese steels in a circular economy.

simultaneously while being alloyed mostly with common elements such as carbon, manganese, silicon, and aluminum. Steels for automotive application currently face different development trends. First of all, the design of cars will change drastically due to increasing electrification, leading to the need of higher-strength steels for lightweighting to compensate for the battery weight, as well as high formable steels (such as high-strength low-alloyed steels) for complex forming processes for purpose-based vehicles.^[3] On the other hand, the steel industry is confronted with the disruptive change from iron ore- and coke-based steel production by the blast furnace to a more sustainable production, focusing on the recycling of steel scrap in the electric arc furnace with additional production of iron by direct reduction. While the environmental impact of the produced steel can be drastically reduced, recycling

1. Introduction

Steel is the dominant material for automotive vehicles,^[1] as due to the large variety of chemical compositions as well as thermo-mechanical processing routes, a wide range of strength–ductility combinations can be achieved.^[2] For a long time, increasing strength was synonymous with a decrease in ductility. However, recently this correlation was broken by the introduction of the third-generation advanced high-strength steels (3G-AHSS), which can achieve both high strength and high ductility

will lead to an increase of residual elements in the produced steel,^[4] as most of the scrap contaminants like Cu^[5] cannot be extracted from the steel melt or the solid scrap to economically feasible boundary conditions.^[6] Tramp elements in steels are defined as the elements which are not added on purpose. These elements cannot be removed from steels by a simple oxidation process during steelmaking or refining because they do not oxidize preferentially in the presence of iron due to the high oxygen partial pressure of their oxides.^[7] Conversely, the residual elements are also generally undesired but can be removed partially from the steel because they partition to slag or dust as opposed to steel to some extent. Therefore, the tramp elements are more dangerous as they cannot be removed easily.^[7] The major tramp elements that are expected to alloy into steel as a consequence of adoption of higher amounts of steel scrap are Cu, Sn, Ni, Cr and Mo,^[8] whereas some others such as As, Sb, Cd, Bi, Co, W etc. may also be present in negligible amounts.

Medium-manganese steels (MMnS), which is a candidate material for 3G-AHSS, have been extensively investigated during the past decade^[9–13] and can be applied either as sheet material or forging components.^[14,15] These steels utilize Mn contents in the range of ≈3.5–10 wt% and can retain high amounts of austenite at room temperature in a ferritic/martensitic matrix due to partitioning of Mn and C into austenite,^[16,17] see **Figure 1**.

The high amount of retained austenite (RA) introduces high strain hardening capabilities, required for cold forming, caused

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DOI: 10.1002/srin.202400841

Figure 1. Intercritical annealing as a processing variant of MMnS and the schematic influence of tramp elements on the transformation temperatures (austenite transformation start and finish temperatures A_{c1} and A_{c3} respectively) and the optimum intercritical annealing temperature to achieve highest amount of RA, T_{peak} .^[14]

by transformation-induced martensite in these steels known as the TRIP effect.^[18–20] Also, MMnS have been studied for their use in hot stamping (press hardening) where a host of benefits are expected.^[21–24] In both cases (cold or hot forming), MMnS can achieve excellent combinations of ultrahigh strength (800–1700 MPa) and tensile elongation (10–40%).

The information on the effect of tramp elements on 3G-AHSS such as MMnS is scarce in literature as the research on the effect of residual elements has focused so far mostly only ultralow to low carbon steels^[25] and only recently the scope was extended to alloyed steels.^[26] Furthermore, although the MMnS are still mostly investigated on the laboratory scale, these steels have great potential to be produced via the electric arc furnace route in the circular economy. The excellent mechanical properties of MMnS rely to a great extent on their multiphase microstructure obtained by different thermomechanical treatments. Therefore, the effect of the impurities from recycling-caused variations is of major relevance to adjust production processes of these steels.

Thus, in this work a theoretical approach was taken to predict the RA fraction of a medium-manganese 3G-AHSS in the presence of selected tramp elements employing thermodynamic software ThermoCalc and available empirical equations in literature. The considered tramp elements in this study are the ones which are expected to be dominant in their concentration in a circular economy: Cu, Ni, Cr, and Mo. Individual effects of these tramp elements as well as their combined effects were investigated by varying their contents systematically for a better understanding. Since the excellent mechanical properties of MMnS are mostly derived from their high RA fractions in the microstructure,^[5,7,8] the prediction results are presented and discussed in terms of RA fractions as a function of processing temperature. An emphasis in analysis has been given on the processing temperatures corresponding to the maximum amount of RA at room temperature for a particular composition. The present work not only elucidates the microstructural effects of tramp elements on the selected MMnS, but also provides guidelines for selecting

the optimum processing temperature and lay a foundation for the future work that needs to be conducted in this area. The aim of this simulative assessment is to estimate the technical limits of the recycled fractions in the production of MMnS. This study also identifies the changes in transformations temperatures and processing behavior. The analysis represents a fundamental consideration for development of new MMnS to design the steels with increased recycled steel fractions and thus contribute to a more sustainable steel industry.

2. Experimental Section

The computational simulations were performed for several MMnS chemistries with a base alloy composition of Fe–0.2C–4.5Mn (composition in wt% here and henceforth if otherwise not mentioned). Manganese and carbon concentrations are rather low in comparison to the general alloying range of MMnS, as this is beneficial for low-alloy cost, relative ease of industrial processability, and good weldability. Individual additions of Ni, Cu, Cr, and Mo as well as their combined presence due to different amounts of steel scrap additions, that is, four hypothetical amounts: 25, 50, 75, and 100 wt% scrap, during steelmaking were considered. For the individual tramp element additions, a small concentration interval of 0.1–0.5 wt% was used considering their expected concentration levels in steels and to capture the effects in small steps. For Cr, two additional levels (1 and 1.5 wt%) were used considering that Cr was used as a deliberate alloying element in MMnS in literature.^[27] In case of scrap additions, the concentration of each element in the alloy was assumed to be linearly proportional to the amount of scrap used. For 25% scrap addition, the resulting concentrations of Ni, Cu, and Mo in the steel were assumed to be 0.1 wt% each, whereas the Cr content was assumed to be 0.15 wt% considering expected higher concentrations of Cr in steel scraps. These values are based on experience of the authors in this area. It should be noted that the exact resulting concentrations of tramp elements due to recycling may vary from these assumptions depending on scrap quality and many other factors during the steelmaking process such as the availability and affordability of the steel refining processes. In any case, the actual amounts of the tramp elements for 50, 75, or 100% scrap-based steelmaking can be lower than the assumed values in this study because efficient refining processes can bring down their amounts. Thus, the present study provides a “conservative scenario” when higher amounts of steel scraps would be used. This is plausible particularly when the deleterious effects of the tramp elements are of concern. Therefore, the “model study” in this article is useful and provides an important perspective on the MMnS microstructures with the expected theoretical contaminations. The alloy systems as well as the concentrations of different added elements are shown in **Table 1**.

To achieve the high amount of RA at room temperature, MMnS were usually heat treated in the intercritical temperature range followed by cooling to room temperature.^[9–13,18,20,28] During intercritical heat treatment Mn and C partitioned to the austenite phase to increase the chemical stability and prevent martensite formation during cooling to room temperature. Therefore, heat treatment or processing of the steels at

Table 1. Alloy systems and their composition ranges (in wt%), along with the suitable M_s equations used in this work.

Alloy system	Concentration of tramp elements	Equations for M_s
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-xNi	$x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$	$539-423C-30.4Mn-17.7Ni^{[60]}$
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-xCu	$x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$	$550-361C-39Mn-10Cu^{[61]}$
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-xCr	$x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5$	$539-423C-30.4Mn-12.1Cr^{[60]}$
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-xMo	$x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$	$539-423C-30.4Mn-7.5Mo^{[61]}$
0.2C-4.5Mn-x ₁ Ni-x ₂ Cu-x ₃ Cr-x ₄ Mo (25 wt% scrap)	$x_1 = x_2 = x_4 = 0.1, x_3 = 0.15$	$550-361C-39Mn-20Cr-17Ni-10Cu-5Mo^{[61]}$
0.2C-4.5Mn-x ₁ Ni-x ₂ Cu-x ₃ Cr-x ₄ Mo (50 wt% scrap)	$x_1 = x_2 = x_4 = 0.2, x_3 = 0.3$	
0.2C-4.5Mn-x ₁ Ni-x ₂ Cu-x ₃ Cr-x ₄ Mo (75 wt% scrap)	$x_1 = x_2 = x_4 = 0.3, x_3 = 0.45$	
0.2C-4.5Mn-x ₁ Ni-x ₂ Cu-x ₃ Cr-x ₄ Mo (100 wt% scrap)	$x_1 = x_2 = x_4 = 0.4, x_3 = 0.6$	

temperatures within the intercritical temperature ranges was considered and the resulting microstructures after cooling were determined.

The equilibrium calculations were performed using the thermodynamic software ThermoCalc version 2022b. The database of TCFE10 was used for all the alloy systems. In case of Cr-added steels, data from TCFE10 was compared with other versions of the database, for example, TCFE7, TCFE8, and TCFE9.

At first, the equilibrium phase fractions of the alloys were calculated for the entire temperature range from liquid phase till room temperature at an interval of 10 °C. The equilibrium transformation temperatures (i.e., the ferrite and austenite transformation temperatures, A_{e1} and A_{e3} , respectively) were also obtained for each alloy. Then, the equilibrium compositions of the intercritical and supercritical austenite were calculated as a function of temperature. These austenite compositions were used to calculate the theoretical martensite start temperatures (M_s). For alloys with different elements, suitable M_s equations containing those elements were used, as listed in Table 1. The phase fractions at room temperature (30 °C) for the alloys were calculated by computing the fraction of fresh martensite and thereby the fraction of RA using Koistinen–Marburger formula^[29] as shown in Equation (1)

$$V_\gamma = e^{[-1.1 \times 10^{-2} (M_s - T_q)]} \quad (1)$$

where V_γ is the volume fraction of RA and T_q is the quenching temperature (i.e., room temperature or 30 °C) from the heat treatment temperature. While applying the Koistinen–Marburger formula, it is assumed that the steels will experience martensitic transformation during cooling from high temperature to room temperature because of high hardenability in the presence of relatively elevated amounts of Mn and C.^[30] The same methodology was applied for simulating RA fraction of the medium-Mn steels from literature having similar chemistries and the computed RA fractions were further compared with the experimental data reported in literature at specified temperatures.

3. Results and Discussion

The simulation results were analyzed for each of the added tramp elements separately, as well as for their combined additions. The analysis provides guidance on selecting the processing

temperatures during intercritical annealing for obtaining the best combination of strength and ductility. As the ductility in MMnS emanates mainly from their RA contents, effects of tramp elements on the behavior of RA are presented and discussed below. The maximum achievable content of RA in an alloy is expressed as RA_{max} and the corresponding heat treatment or processing temperature is denoted as T_{peak} . First, the effects of individual additions of the tramp elements are assessed, followed by an analysis of combined additions.

3.1. Effect of Ni

The effect of Ni on the phase transformation behavior of MMnS is shown in **Figure 2** as a function of heat treatment temperature. Addition of Ni increases the RA_{max} (by 2 vol% with 0.5Ni), as observed in Figure 2a, while the T_{peak} experiences a shift to lower temperatures (by 6 °C with 0.5Ni). The amount of RA is dependent on the amount and thermal stability of intercritical austenite determined by its composition. The amount of intercritical austenite is increased with addition of Ni and the A_{C3} – A_{C1} temperature range increases (**Table 2**). Similar to Mn, Ni is known as an austenite stabilizer increasing the austenite phase region.^[31] The composition of intercritical austenite is crucial in determining the M_s . For the industrially relevant range of temperature, that is, 600–700 °C, the composition of austenite varies distinctly for three temperature ranges, that is, temperature 1) below, 2) at, and 3) above cementite dissolution temperature (A_{CM}). Below A_{CM} , the C and Mn contents in intercritical austenite of Ni added steels are lower than that without Ni. This leads to an overall increase in M_s and higher martensite fractions at room temperature. However, as the initial fraction of intercritical austenite is higher for Ni added steels, despite having marginally higher M_s , they yield higher amounts of RA when heat treated below the A_{CM} . At the A_{CM} , amount of C in intercritical austenite is the maximum. The addition of Ni results in lowering of A_{CM} (641 °C for 0.5 wt% Ni and 650 °C for 0.1 wt% Ni) as well as lowering of the maximum C in intercritical austenite (Figure 2c). As a resulting effect of increased Ni (Figure 2b) and lower C, the M_s of intercritical austenite at A_{CM} is lower (76 °C for 0.5 wt% Ni and 95 °C for 0.1 wt% Ni) for Ni added steels. This leads to higher RA_{max} and lower T_{peak} with Ni addition when the steels are heat treated at the A_{CM} . For heat treating above the A_{CM} , there is marginal decrease of RA with Ni due to slight increase in M_s temperature.

Figure 2. a) Amount of RA calculated for the alloy composition of Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-(0-0.5)Ni, b) concentration of Mn, Ni, and c) C in intercritical austenite for 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 Ni added steels, all plotted against processing temperature.

Table 2. Equilibrium transformation temperature and calculated M_s , RA_{max} , and T_{peak} for various alloys.

Alloy system	A_{c1} [°C]	A_{c3} [°C]	RA_{max} [vol%]	T_{peak} [°C]	M_s at T_{peak} [°C]
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn	550	730	23.1 ^{a)} , 32.2	647	81 ^{a)} , 51
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-0.5Ni	480	730	25.3 ^{a)}	641	76 ^{a)}
Fe-0.2-4.5Mn-0.5Cu	482	730	33.4	642	52
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-0.5Cr	541	730	14.6 ^{a)}	663	139 ^{a)}
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-0.5Mo	540	740	20.4 ^{a)}	647	88 ^{a)}
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-0.1Ni-0.1Cu-0.15Cr-0.1Mo	452	726	29.3	640	42
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-0.2Ni-0.2Cu-0.3Cr-0.2Mo	450	723	28.1	630	27
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-0.3Ni-0.3Cu-0.45Cr-0.3Mo	400	721	28.3	630	36
Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-0.4Ni-0.4Cu-0.6Cr-0.4Mo	320	718	26.2	620	22

^{a)}refers to M_s calculation by.^[60]

3.2. Effect of Cu

The addition of 0.5Cu lowers the A_{e1} by more than 60 °C, that is, from 550 to 482 °C, which is similar to addition of 0.5Ni (Table 3). Therefore, the intercritical austenite phase region with respect to temperature is wider. However, the changes in RA_{max} and T_{peak} with Cu addition are marginal (Figure 3a). The cementite dissolution temperature A_{CM} and corresponding peak C content in intercritical austenite are lower for Cu added steels (Figure 3c). Compared to Ni addition, the nature

of the RA curve is different for Cu alloying. This is due to the difference in available M_s equations with these two elements (Table 1), specifically the coefficient for C largely differs for both the equations. There is a small plateau observed for steels without Cu for the heat treatment temperature range of 640–650 °C (inset of Figure 3a). The temperature range for the plateau becomes narrower with increasing Cu content. The Cu partitioning in intercritical austenite and the phase transformation behavior remain similar to that of Ni as described in Section 3.1.

Table 3. Types of equilibrium carbides as obtained from calculations using various ThermoCalc databases in the temperature range of 300–1000 °C for the base alloy of Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn.

Database	Cr content [wt%]				
	0.1	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.5
TCFE7 (V7.0)	Cementite, M_7C_3 , M_5C_2 , $M_{23}C_6$	Cementite, M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$	M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$	M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$	M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$
TCFE8 (V8.2)	Cementite, M_7C_3 , M_5C_2 , $M_{23}C_6$	Cementite, M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$	M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$	M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$	M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$
TCFE9 (V9.3)	Cementite, $M_{23}C_6$	Cementite, $M_{23}C_6$	Cementite, $M_{23}C_6$	Cementite, M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$	M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$
TCFE10 (V10.1)	Cementite, $M_{23}C_6$	Cementite, $M_{23}C_6$	Cementite, $M_{23}C_6$	Cementite, M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$	M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$

Figure 3. a) Amount of RA calculated for the alloy composition of Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-(0-0.5)Cu; inset highlights the region near RA_{max} , and b) concentration of Mn, Cu, and c) C in intercritical austenite for 0.1, 0.3, 0.5Cu added steels, all plotted against processing temperature.

3.3. Effect of Cr

Figure 4a shows the effect of Cr addition on the RA fraction in MMnS plotted against the heat treatment temperature. It is evident from the RA curves that the phase transformation behavior is different for Cr addition than that with Ni and Cu additions. Cr content has a strong influence on RA_{max} . The RA_{max} decreases by 5–15 vol% with increase in Cr from 0.1 to 1 wt%. Moreover, there is a wide-temperature plateau of nearly constant RA_{max} observed instead of a single T_{peak} for higher Cr content. The width of this temperature plateau corresponding to RA_{max} increases significantly with increase in Cr content. The reason for such an influence of Cr is the formation of different metal carbides over the range of temperature being investigated. The equilibrium phase fractions as calculated from ThermoCalc show the presence of three different carbides, namely, cementite, M_7C_3 , and $M_{23}C_6$. For ThermoCalc database TCFE10, there are two, that is, cementite, $M_{23}C_6$, or three, that is, cementite, $M_{23}C_6$, M_7C_3 equilibrium carbides depending on the Cr content. The C in intercritical austenite is much lower in Cr added steels in

comparison to Cr-free steels (Figure 4c). This is due to the loss of C in different carbides. The carbide dissolution temperatures also vary with the type of carbides. For example, in 1Cr steel the carbide dissolution temperatures are: 643.4 °C for $M_{23}C_6$, 662.7 °C for cementite, and 676.6 °C for M_7C_3 . This leads to change in the C content of intercritical austenite at corresponding dissolution temperatures (Figure 4c). The Cr content in austenite, as shown in Figure 4b, also increases with heat treatment temperature until the M_7C_3 carbide is dissolved.

From the current predictions in Figure 4a, it is evident that the effect of Cr as the tramp element can be detrimental to the amount of achievable RA, although a more or less constant amount of RA over a wide processing temperature range can be achieved. This behavior would be beneficial for industrial production of these alloys giving a robust window of processing temperature in order to avoid microstructural variations since temperature variations in industrial process can be significant (up to ± 15 °C).

It is interesting to note that, for ThermoCalc database versions V7.0, V8.2, V9.3, and V10.1 for databases TCFE7, 8, 9, and 10,

Figure 4. a) Amount of RA calculated for the alloy composition of Fe-0.2C-4.5Mn-(0-1.5)Cr, b) concentration of Mn, Cr, c) C in intercritical austenite for 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, and 1.5Cr added steels, all plotted against processing temperature.

respectively, the types of carbides are different. Table 3 summarizes these carbides obtained in equilibrium calculations for the base chemistry of Fe–0.2C–4.5Mn using four different ThermoCalc database versions.

The differences in the fractions of other phases, especially the carbides, in equilibrium calculations influence the calculated fractions of RA content. Below the carbide dissolution temperature, most of the carbon is bounded in the carbides. So, the amount and type of carbides are important for the calculation. As observed from Table 3, there can be two or three types of carbides predicted by different databases. All these carbides will have different dissolution temperatures, as mentioned before. So, the carbon content of intercritical austenite will greatly vary. The carbide dissolution temperature corresponds to the peak C content in intercritical austenite, that in turn gives rise to the maximum RA content (RA_{max}). However, with multiple carbides, there can be difference in the peak C content (see Figure 4c with 0.5 wt% Cr), leading to difference in RA_{max} . Therefore, the choice of thermodynamic database for the calculations remains crucial. The effect of Cr on RA stabilization was previously studied by Kang et al. using ThermoCalc databases SSOL2 and TCFE7^[32] in contrast to TCFE10 in this study. Therefore, it is to be noted that the nature of the current RA curves for Cr added steels differs from this previous study. In particular, the shapes of the RA curves obtained by Kang et al. for high Cr contents (0.5–1.5 wt%) are flatter in shape around the plateau compared to the more slanted nature of the RA plateau predicted in the current study. This difference is due to the variations in other equilibrium phase fractions calculated from different ThermoCalc databases. Moreover, the intercritical austenite composition also changes with different databases due to differences in carbide formation. This leads to variations in M_s and consequently the RA calculations.

3.4. Effect of Mo

With Mo addition in the MMnS, a different behavior of RA_{max} and the associated T_{peak} is observed although the nature of the RA curves remains somewhat similar compared to that of steels

without any Mo addition (Figure 5a). With increase in Mo concentrations beyond 0.1 wt% two adjacent peaks for RA_{max} at two corresponding T_{peak} temperatures are observed. In the inset of Figure 5a the RA curves with an enlarged view of the RA_{max} peaks are shown. It should also be noted that the difference between two adjacent T_{peak} temperatures corresponding to two RA_{max} becomes larger with higher Mo content. Such behavior of the RA curve can be explained by the predicted equilibrium carbide fractions. Figure 5b reveals the presence of two major carbides in the temperature range of T_{peak1} corresponding to RA_{max1} peak at lower temperature and T_{peak2} corresponding to RA_{max2} peak at higher temperature. For the lower Mo content of 0.1 wt%, only cementite is observed. With increase in Mo content, the cementite fraction decreases, whereas the M_7C_3 carbide increases in amount. The dissolution temperature for M_7C_3 is higher than that of cementite. The difference in dissolution temperature increases with increase in Mo content. The opposing effects of formation and dissolution of these carbides result in two adjacent peaks in the C content in intercritical austenite, as displayed in the inset of Figure 5b. Finally, the effect of this is reflected in the two peaks of the RA_{max} . The difference in dissolution temperatures of both the carbides is reflected in peak temperatures T_{peak1} and T_{peak2} corresponding to RA_{max1} and RA_{max2} with increase in Mo content.

3.5. Effects of Various Amounts of Scrap

In practical situations, industrial steel scrap may have more than one or all of the tramp elements in various concentrations which will pass on to the produced steel.^[4,8] While the utilization of high amounts of scrap is beneficial for the steel production in terms of the environmental impact,^[33] the concentration of tramp elements increases with the share of scrap during steel production. To simulate the effects of the use of industrial steel scrap during steelmaking, as mentioned earlier, four different amounts of steel scrap (i.e., 25–100 wt% of scrap in the produced steel) were considered. The calculated RA curves of the scrap added MMnS are shown in Figure 6a in comparison with the steel without containing the tramp elements. It is observed that

Figure 5. a) Amount of RA calculated for the alloy composition of Fe–0.2C–4.5Mn–(0–0.5)Mo; inset shows the temperature region near RA_{max} peaks, and b) phase fraction of different carbides for 0.1–0.5Mo added steels; inset shows the C content in intercritical austenite for 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 wt% Mo added steels. All are plotted against the processing temperature.

Figure 6. a) Amount of RA calculated for 25, 50, 75, and 100 wt% scrap addition during production of MMnS and b) global phase fractions at room temperature (30 °C) predicted for 25 wt% scrap addition.

both the RA_{max} and the corresponding T_{peak} are lower with the increase in the amount of scrap. In addition, the RA curves exhibit a wider region of variable RA. However, at lower temperatures than T_{peak} , the slope of the RA curves against processing temperature remains similar, although the amount of RA is higher for higher amounts of steel scrap used. This is a combined effect of all the added elements. The broadening of the RA curve is presumably due to the larger intercritical austenite region in presence of austenite stabilizing elements Cu and Ni (see Table 2 for transformation temperatures). On the other hand, the presence of Cr and Mo reduces the RA_{max} and T_{peak} . It is important to state that the formation and dissolution of equilibrium carbides are crucial in determining the composition of intercritical austenite, which in turn governs the thermal stability of austenite and consequently the martensite formation and the RA fraction at room temperature.

The predicted phase fractions at room temperature for the representative case of 25 wt% scrap addition are shown in Figure 6b. The equilibrium phases with amount less than 1 vol% were not considered. The industrially relevant temperature region, that is, 600–700 °C, should be considered for obtaining higher RA (about 20–25 vol%) along with ferrite, martensite, and cementite.

3.6. Critical Assessment and Future Directions

From the current predictions, it appears that individual additions of the tramp elements do not always have a detrimental effect on the desired microstructure of MMnS. Ni and Cu in their considered range up to 0.5 wt% do not decrease the maximum achievable amount of RA; Ni rather increases it slightly (Figure 7a). The effects of Cr and Mo on the amount of RA are of mixed type. Increasing the Cr content decreases the maximum achievable RA content but also provides a large temperature window where less variations in microstructure can be assured (Figure 7a). Also, Mo reduces the maximum achievable RA content less drastically than Cr. Moreover, although it gives rise to two RA_{max} peaks, the temperature range where these two peaks occur can be considered as a processing window where less variations in

microstructure are expected if the steel is heat treated in that temperature range (Figure 7b).

The combined additions, which are the most realistic situations in a circular economy, appear to have a detrimental effect on the desired third-generation AHSS microstructure of MMnS. When present together, they reduce the maximum amount of RA (Figure 8a) but does not alter the shape of the RA curve to indicate any wide processing window. However, the T_{peak} decreases with increasing scrap content (Figure 8a) and the RA content increases for lower processing temperatures. The effect of the tramp elements on MMnS is not limited to an increased austenite fraction,^[34,35] but also influences the properties of the austenite itself, as Cu for instances increases the lattice parameter^[36] and also increases the stability^[37] of the austenite phase. Overall, the general effect of Cu in MMnS seems to be positive, as strength,^[38,39] strain hardening, and Charpy impact toughness^[35] can be improved due to the precipitation of nanometer-sized Cu precipitates. Molybdenum increases the hardenability of MMnS,^[40,41] which needs to be addressed during the design of the thermomechanical process. Furthermore, molybdenum addition holds the potential to reduce the grain boundary embrittlement of MMnS,^[17,42] by preventing segregation of manganese to the austenite grain boundaries during heat treatments. Chromium was reported to refine the microstructure through the precipitation of nanometer-sized precipitates,^[42,43] which can increase the hardness of the MMnS with a minor compromise on the toughness.^[44] However, these observations were done on MMnS with significant higher-chromium concentrations; therefore, these observations might not be transferable. Nickel, if coalloyed with aluminum, can lead to precipitation of a B2 phase, which positively influences hardness and tensile strength^[45] and, similar to Cu, increases the stability of the RA.^[46] The research on the effect of the abovementioned elements focuses on concentrations which are far larger than the expected “tramp” concentrations; therefore, the transferability of the availability knowledge is limited. In summary, the effect of each single-tramp element as well as their combined addition must not be detrimental for the final performance of the steel. So, adjustments of the optimal heat treatment parameters for

Figure 7. Comparison of a) T_{peak} , b) RA_{max} , and c) partitioning of C, and d) partitioning of Ni, Cu, Cr, Mo in intercritical austenite as a function of elemental concentration in steels. The data for reproducing this results is provided as Supporting Information.

MMnS must be developed, while dealing with such elements. This demonstrates the importance of the manuscript as a first, theoretical assessment.

It should be mentioned that the current predictions are based on equilibrium microstructures at high temperature which are assumed to be valid, in general, for a long soaking time at a particular temperature. However, in industrial heat treatments (e.g., during continuous annealing or reheating prior to hot press forming), the soaking duration is often very short (e.g., 2–5 min). Such durations are particularly considered shorter in the presence of slow-diffusing large substitutional element in iron such as Mn which is the key element in MMnS. Diffusion kinetics is

not included in the present work and needs to be addressed in future scope. In actual industrial scenario, the microstructural features like rolled and elongated grains, Mn bands, etc. will have influence on diffusion distances during thermal cycles. This, in turn, will influence the fraction, composition, and stability of intercritical austenite as opposed to the predicted values from ThermoCalc. Therefore, the predicted results (interpretable in terms of RA_{max} and T_{peak}) may vary from real nonequilibrium experiments, as also shown in literature.^[18,47] The experimental validation of the methodology followed in the present work was demonstrated by De Moor et al.^[48] The work demonstrated the effect of Mn and C partitioning in the stabilization of intercritical austenite of medium-Mn steels. The predicted fraction of RA at room temperature was compared with experimental data. It was observed that the model underpredicted the fraction of RA at higher annealing temperatures. The current work also compares the experimental data from literature with the predicted RA fractions as computed with the present method of calculation for eight steel chemistries which have Mn contents in the same range as in the present work.^[48–55] These comparisons are shown in **Figure 9**. It is important to note that the processing route for each of the alloys in terms of time, temperature, forging/rolling conditions before annealing was different (Figure 9a). Additionally, the steel chemistries included additional elements like Si and Al in higher contents. Nevertheless, the comparison shows the same trend as shown by De Moor et al.^[48] and Rana et al.^[18] that at higher annealing temperatures (>650 °C), the simulation underpredicts the RA contents. The higher annealing temperature corresponds to the region with higher fraction of intercritical austenite and without the presence of carbides. The amount of C in the intercritical austenite is therefore lower leading to lower stability of austenite and consequently lower RA fractions. However, in real nonequilibrium conditions, the C and Mn enrichments could be faster in the intercritical austenite owing to the crystallographic defects like vacancies and dislocations in mechanically worked material, leading to increased stability of austenite. In addition, the local Mn gradients may lead to increased RA fractions as compared to the predicted RA values based on equilibrium Mn partitioning. The present work, therefore, provides a useful tool to compare the effects of tramp elements in a realistic way. A critical point for the validation of the findings is the limited experimental data for the effect of minor tramp elements on MMnS. As outlined, most of the studies focus on higher alloying concentration, which cannot be considered as tramp element. Therefore, a realistic comparison is, right now, only possible by means of simulations. While elements are added individually in the majority of our investigations, in reality the issue of impurity introduction is of high complexity, as synergistic effects of the different alloying elements will increase or decrease their influence on the properties as well as on processability.^[6] In the case of a joint enrichment of Ni and Cu, for example, it can be assumed that for low Cu contents the negative effects on processability can be compensated by Ni,^[56] as nickel increases the solubility of Cu in the iron matrix and can thus counteract hot embrittlement within certain limits.^[6] Especially the carbide forming elements like Mo and Cr will show synergetic effects, as the precipitation kinetics as well as size and morphology of the carbides will vary depending on the impurity concentration.^[57] For the approach used in this

Figure 8. Comparison of a) RA_{max} and T_{peak}, b) partitioning of C, Mo, and c) partitioning of Ni, Cu, Cr in intercritical austenite as a function of amount of scrap. (The data for reproducing this results is provided as Supporting Information.)

Figure 9. Summary of literature data: a) processing route and their variables and b) comparison of measured data from literature and predicted RA contents using the methodology used in the present work.

work it can be assumed that the majority of interactions between the elements (e.g., the respective effects on the equilibrium transformation temperatures) are included within the ThermoCalc.

Additionally, it should be noted that one of the most prominent tramp elements Sn is excluded in this study because suitable empirical equations to predict M_s temperature in the presence of Sn are not available in literature. In thermokinetic software packages such as JMatPro or MatCalc, Sn is not included. Therefore, for the microstructural predictions in this work pertaining to scrap, added steels must be interpreted with caution. Consequently, this work highlights the importance for producing experimental data on the effects of Sn so that those can be used by researchers. This should be an important future work in the context of circularity of steel manufacturing.

Lastly, it should be mentioned that Cu, Ni, and Sn are highly surface-active elements in steel. During high-temperature processing, if oxidation is allowed, they tend to segregate at the scale-substrate interface, grain boundaries, and can also get occluded in the scale depending on temperature. This may

reduce their amount in the matrix.^[58,59] This can also influence the phase transformation in the matrix, with an outcome of less severe effect of the tramp elements on the microstructures. It is suggested that future experimental work be undertaken in the areas mentioned in this subsection to clarify the effects.

4. Conclusion

The increasing amount of recycled fractions in the material flow of steel production will influence the chemical composition of high-strength steels and consequently their performance and behavior. From the current work on predicting the microstructures to uncover the effects of tramp elements on a lean MMnS, the following major conclusions can be drawn. 1) All the four alloying elements investigated in the study have a decreasing effect of A_c1 temperature for Ni with the most prominent effect and Cr the least. 2) The intercritical austenite fraction and the partitioning of elements largely determine the RA fraction in

the medium-Mn steels. Ni and Cu have an effect on the former by lowering the A_{c1} , whereas Cr and Mo alter the latter by forming equilibrium metal carbides. 3) The overall transformation behavior of austenite in presence of Ni and Cu does not vary significantly due to its combined effects on austenite stabilization and cementite formation. 4) Cr decreases the maximum achievable RA but gives a robust processing window. Particularly with high Cr contents, the RA plateau is strongly dependent on the dissolution temperatures of various carbides. 5) Mo addition causes a small decrease in maximum RA and gives rise to a peculiar effect of two adjacent RA peaks due to the opposing effects of formation and dissolution of cementite and M_7C_3 carbide. 6) The combined presence of Ni, Cu, Cr, and Mo as a result of increasing steel scrap addition during steel production decreases the maximum achievable content of RA, shifts the corresponding processing temperature to a lower side, and increases the RA content for lower processing temperatures.

In summary, the effect of different alloying elements introduced by recycling is manageable in the case of MMnS. By understanding the mutual influence on the phase transformation, the thermal treatments can be adjusted for the varying chemical compositions and therefore enable a circular steel production.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge the funding received for this work in part from the European Research Executive Agency (REA) under grant agreement no. 101112425. Also, the authors from RWTH Aachen University would like to thank Ms. Neslihan Altinel for her help in data processing.

Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

medium-manganese steels, microstructure predictions, retained austenites, steel scraps, tramp elements

Received: October 21, 2024

Revised: December 24, 2024

Published online:

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